

ISic0793

I.Sicily inscription 0793

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Vittorio Bottini,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates**

38.1992517, 15.5566385

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3570

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus) □
2. L(uci) □ Ostri □ Vesoñiâni
3. vix(it) □ an(nis) □ XXXVI □
4. me(n)s(ibus) □ III □ dieb(us) □ XV □

Apparatus

Text after Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

To the Shades of the Underworld of Lucius Ostrius Vesonianus. He lived 36 years, 3 months, 15 days.

Translation (en)

Alle ombre dell'aldilà di Lucio Ostrio Vesoniano. Egli visse 36 anni, 3 mesi, 15 giorni.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175729

EDR 076854

EDCS 9300941

PHI 313625

Bibliography

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